

Engaging Fashion Brand Followers on Social Media Platforms - an Explorative Study of Fashion Brands

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Abstract:

Background This paper adds to literature by analyzing the brand generated social media content on multiple platforms and its impact on customer engagement.

Methods The study analyses how fifty fashion brands express themselves through brand generated social media content on six platforms. In this paper Customer Engagement has been used as a tool to evaluate a brand's marketing efforts on social media platforms. Customer Engagement rate can be seen as a measure of the distance between a brand and their customers. Analysis was done using descriptive statistics, Correlation Coefficient and Scatter Plot.

Results: The results of this paper show that the degree of customer engagement can vary based on the day of posting. The study also demonstrates how different social media platforms can show either positive or negative impact on customer engagement levels based on average posting per month.

Conclusion: This study adds to the body of knowledge on fashion marketing and consumer engagement by providing empirical evidence in favor of the theory that high posting rate may not always result in high customer engagement. High average posting rate may impact social media customer engagement positively or negatively, depending on platform to platform. Also, the day of posting impacts customer engagement levels. Marketers need to analyze each platform individually to see what works best for the brand.

Keywords: Brand-generated content, Brand engagement, Fashion marketing, social media, User engagement

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1. Introduction

Information and communication technology use, particularly social media use, has expanded globally. The importance of brands using social media platforms in India is evident from the articles that state India has more than 820 million active internet users. In the last year, one in four urban Indian online consumers used social media apps for their purchases [1]. Eighty-nine percent of internet users are active on social media every day, with an average Indian spending 194 minutes on Social Media (SM) each day [2]. SM platforms are a collection of web-based tools that enables the creation and sharing of content. These SM platforms are built on the conceptual framework and technologies that underpins the World Wide Web [3]. Marketing strategies have evolved with the new dynamics of the market [4]. This adaptation to the changing world has been seen not just in large enterprises but in SMEs as well [5]. As a result, Consumer Engagement (CE) in particular has gained attention in the research environment. CE in the world of SM has been defined as “active relationship with the brand as personified by the website or other computer-mediated entities” [6]. An increasing array of channels are being used by brands to communicate and engage with present and potential customers. These SM interactions have been known to have an impact on customer purchase intentions [7] and on brand loyalty [8]. SM content is either brand generated or user generated. CE on SM has been studied based on user generated content by many researchers [9, 10 & 11]. CE has been studied from the perspective of influencer generated content too [12,13]. Brands are using a variety of channels to connect with consumers globally, which makes it more difficult to gauge the impact and success of

each channel. To understand CE better, many researchers have worked on Instagram [14, 15] or Facebook [16, 17] as a platform, but not considered multiple platforms together from the perspective of brand generated content. This paper attempts to fill this gap by analyzing brand generated content on six social media platforms, namely Facebook (FB), Instagram (IG), YouTube (YT), Twitter (X), Pinterest (P) and LinkedIn (LI).

1.1 Research Question

1.1.1 Research question 1: Researcher wants to analyze the brand-generated content on chosen social media platforms to understand the marketing strategies and usage of different social media platforms.

1.1.2 Research question 2: Researcher wants to understand the correlation between customer engagement rate and average posts per month on IG and YT.

1.2 How is Customer Engagement calculated

The number of 'Likes' and 'Comments' on any post is a useful indicator of how customers interact with that brand [18, 19 & 20]. The engagement rate is calculated as total engagements divided by total followers, multiplied by 100.

Total Engagement = the sum of all interactions (shares, comments, reactions, etc.).

Total Followers = the number of people who follow the account.

2. Methods

In this research paper, brand generated content of fifty brands have been studied on multiple platforms. Data has been collected between 9th June 2024 to 11th June 2024.

2.1 Data Collection

Two big retail companies Aditya Birla Fashion and Retail Ltd (revenue increased 18.3% to ₹3,406.7 crore against ₹2,879.7 crore in the year-ago period) [21] and Reliance Retail (10.6% rise in revenue at ₹76,627 crore, up from ₹69,288 crore in the year-ago period) [22] were used as starting points. Brands under the umbrella of these two companies were studied and then moving on, direct competition of the brands were picked up. Using snowball sampling, websites of 51 fashion brands with both offline and online presence in India were visited. One brand was rejected as all SM handles of this brand were inactive since 2020. MBOs were kept out of the scope of the research. Each brand's website was visited and link to the SM handles were followed from their website to ensure correct handle. Some or all of the following platforms appeared on the websites: Facebook (FB), Instagram (IG), YouTube (YT), Twitter (X), Pinterest (P) and LinkedIn (LI). Content of the 50 brands was analyzed on all the six platforms. Tick-Tok being a platform not available in India, was not considered for analysis. Spotify was mentioned in only 2 out of 50 brands so this platform too was not considered. This research covers data collected from post-covid years only, from Jan 2022 till the first week of June 2024.

In 2023, Instagram was the most popular SM platform with 74.70% of internet users in India [23]. As of January 2024, India had the largest Instagram audience in the world with a total of 362 million Instagram users [24]. IG was mentioned on maximum websites (96%) and none of the brands had an inactive IG handle. IG was picked up for further extensive research. FB, X and IG have similar content for most brands, so FB and X were not considered for further in-depth research. As a second platform YT was studied. The importance of YouTube in fashion marketing and communication is well documented in research [25, 26 & 27]. For research question two, IG and YT were studied in further detail.

For data collection, there are multiple AI based tools available like Social Blade, Like Alyzer, Phlanx etc. On seeing the reports generated by multiple data scraping AI tools, Phlanx was chosen based on the in-depth report. The use of this AI based tool, Phlanx, is well documented in research [28-31]. Using AI based tool Phlanx, a total of 89 detailed reports of all active handles of IG (50) and YT (39) for the selected fashion brands were generated and studied on two parameters of customer engagement rate and average number of posts per month.

3. Results

3.1 Results

Research question 1: Analysis of the content on social media (SM) platforms

How often a SM platform is mentioned on a brand’s website shows the importance and acceptance of the platform. On the home page of 96% of brand websites link to the IG handle was mentioned. 94% of the website home pages had the link to FB handle. Only one brand did not mention any SM handle on their website. A good following on social media for a fashion brand indicates several key aspects like brand credibility [32], brand popularity and loyalty [33], brand influence and reach [34]. Based on number of followers; 62% of the brands have maximum followers on FB, 28% of the brands have maximum followers on IG and 10% of the brands have almost equal followers on IG and FB. The most common marketing strategy seen on the SM handles is: *Establishing a strong online presence by regular posting of stylized product shoots using storytelling*. This strategy was seen on 96% of brands on IG and 92% of brands on FB. LI as a platform is primarily being used for brand building and job postings, not product promotion. Product range promotion was seen only in 16% of the brands on LI.

3.1.1 Facebook (FB) 94% of brands have a link to their FB handle on the homepage of their website. Particular emphasis on brand story telling is noticed. The art and science of brand storytelling is the use of an engaging narrative to foster empathy and resonance between a company and its customers. Interestingly, 2 brands with large following on FB have stopper posting (inactive) on the handle. Fred Perry (1.6M followers) has not posted on FB since 2021 and Nautica (5.8M followers) has not posted since Aug 2023 on FB.

3.1.2 Instagram (IG) 96% of brands have a link to their IG handle on the homepage of their website. Average posting per month is seen to be as high as 50 posts, to a minimum of 1 post in two months. The brands are communicating their values, beliefs, and distinctiveness through a story that connects with the target audience. Celebrity spotted in the brands clothing is an interesting strategy seen on this platform. All 50 brands had active IG handles. On IG, Friday is the most popular day for brands to post. Least CE is generated on Saturday, Sunday, Tuesday and Wednesday. Maximum CE is generated on Thursday and Friday, followed by Monday.

Table 1: Descriptive data of Instagram posts of 50 brands

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Influences %	50	0	8.0	1.688	1.8367
Male %	50	26	72	51.44	12.341
Female %	50	28	74	48.64	12.245
Authentic Engagements	50	30.4	64800.0	5461.298	11194.6923
Avg. Posts per month	50	52	50.57	16.0126	12.02511
Customer Engagement	50	0.05 %	4.07 %	1.0230 %	1.16944%
Followers	50	2700	61800000	323981.00	9991670.025
Valid N (List wise)	50				

Figure 1: Instagram: Most popular posting days for brand generated content

Figure 2: Instagram: Most popular days for brand-customer interaction for brand generated content

3.1.3 *YouTube (YT)* 78% of brands have a link to their YT handle on the homepage of their website. 39 of 50 brands post their ad campaigns and launch their collection videos on their YT handle, rest of the brands either do not have a YT handle or are inactive on this platform. Highlighting collaborations (28%) with other brands, celebrities and/or Music bands is seen getting good viewership and CE on this platform.

Table 2: Descriptive data of YouTube posts of 39 brands

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Followers	39	1200	1460000	342713.08	400022.287
Avg. views per video	39	39.2	3500000	363150.205	665047.2333
Avg. Engagement per Video (Likes + Commitment)	39	.9	30590	4104.256	8282.8998
Avg. Videos per month	39	.31	30	4.0187	5.68276
Customer Engagement	39	0.01 %	6.01 %	1.2723 %	1.41460 %
Valid N (Listwise)	39				

On YT, Monday and Thursday are the most popular days for brands to post. Least CE is generated on Saturday and Sunday. Maximum CE is generated on Wednesday.

Figure 3: YouTube: Most popular posting days for brand generated content

Figure 4: YouTube: Most popular days for brand-customer interaction for brand generated content

3.1.4 *LinkedIn (LI)* 24% of brands have a link to their LI handle on the homepage of their website. 46% of brands use LI to promote brand’s achievements (brand building) like new store launches, highlighting brand employee’s achievements and Internal Brand events like workshops, seminars etc. 42% of brands use the LI handle to post jobs and internship opportunities. Interestingly, only 18% use LI for both job postings and brand building. 16% of the brands post regularly with latest collection photoshoots on LI.

3.1.5 *Twitter (X)* 76% of brands have a link to their X handle on the homepage of their website. 40% of the brands post either daily or at least 4-5 times a week on X. Surprisingly, 46% of the brand’s X handles are inactive.

3.1.6 *Pinterest (P)* 30% of brands have a link to their P handle on the homepage of their website. 50% of the brands post regularly with latest collection photoshoots on P. Interestingly, 40% of the brand’s P handles are inactive.

Table 3: Comparative analysis of CE on FB, IG and YT

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
FB Customer Engagement	50	.00	.84	.1468	.21183

IG Customer Engagement	50	0.05 %	4.07 %	1.0230%	1.16944 %
YT Customer Engagement	50	0.00 %	25.71 %	1.7626 %	4.34961 %
Valid N 9(Listwise)	50				

Between the most popular three platforms of FB, IG and YT, YT has the highest CE followed by IG.

3.2 Results: Research Question 2: Correlation between engagement rate and Average Posts per month

Correlation Coefficient tests were run to test the correlation between the variables. Avg. posts per month and Customer Engagement has a Correlation Coefficient of (-) 0.454 on IG and 0.411 on YT.

To further understand the directionality of the correlation Scatter Plots were made.

Figure 5: Instagram: Scatter Plot of average posts per month by customer engagement

Average posts per month and Customer Engagement on IG clearly shows a negative correlation whereas on YT the average posts per month and Customer Engagement show a positive correlation.

4. Conclusion

This paper uses customer engagement as a tool to evaluate a brand’s marketing practices on social media platforms. Customer Engagement rate has been seen as a measure of the distance between a brand and its customers. With ever-increasing array of channels being utilized by brands to engage with present/potential customers, effectiveness of each platform needs to be assessed to ensure impact. Research clearly shows IG is the most significant SM platform. There is a negative correlation between CE and high posting frequency on IG but a positive correlation of YT. This shows that brand managers have to dig deeper to understand the posting rate on each platform to maximize CE. The usage of each social media platform needs to be monitored individually to understand the best posting rate/ day to maximize CE. The findings have practical applications for fashion brands in terms of how to use social media more effectively.

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